

Improving Resilience to Extreme Events

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Motivation

Disintegrated hazard management systems often created momentous risk exposures to public, and lack of an exact understanding of the situation (e.g., the scope and impact of the hazard) based on real-time information results in substantial risks to human life and property. There is also need for hazard planners and responders who can use a wide variety of technologies and tools to assist them during an extreme event.

Envisioned DAILY framework

DAILY aims at designing and developing a comprehensive knowledge base, by collecting and analysing the approaches to adaptability and resilience of communities in diverse disasters available in Norway, Europe and the USA, and expanding the currently limited frameworks to any local community.

Figure 1. DAILY framework

Specially DAILY platform has five main responsibilities.

- Aggregate multimodal information
- Semantic integration
- Integrate the new knowledge provided by the crowd
- Present aggregated and structured data
- Direct interaction between users & information provider

Figure 2. DAILY platform

Semantics in DAILY

Semantic representations play an important role in integrating and analysing heterogeneous data from several resources such as social media, meteorological, input from first responders and people to obtain actionable insights and support decision making during extreme climate events.

Figure 3. Semantics in DAILY platform

From social media to semantics

To develop a proper semantic representation, topics related to extreme events from social media data are collected. Further real-time data is analysed in local and global levels. The overview of analysis consists of three components, as shown in below figure.

Figure 3. Overview of social media analysis

To elaborate representation, details such as attributes and relations will be extracted by statistics and machine learning techniques, and they will be verified by field trials with relevant stakeholders.

Future work

The project will enhance communication between citizens and authorities in all phases of the disaster management process: from the identification of the best strategies for increasing resilience to the direct communication before, immediately before, during and after an extreme event strikes, as well as for the sharing of righteous behaviour in case of slow processes affecting the environment and the social living of the community.